

Diazotisation Rearrangement of Tosylhydrazones of *ortho*- and *meta*-Substituted-benzophenones and α -Substituted-acetophenones (Synthesis of Anilides)

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Ortho- and *meta*-substituted-benzophenones (1a-g) and substituted-acetophenones (1h-i) were converted into tosylhydrazones (2a-i) by reacting with *p*-toluenesulphonylhydrazide. Conversion of 2a-i to the anilides (3a-i) was effected with the reagents H₂SO₄ and NaNO₂, and was found to be as facile as in case of the *para*-substituted-benzophenone hydrazones.

PEARSON and Greer¹ first observed that benzophenone hydrazones on diazotisation with sulphuric acid and sodium nitrite undergo arrangement to the corresponding anilides. Literature study revealed that this rearrangement received very little attention probably due to instability of hydrazones and their tendency to form azines spontaneously. Ketone hydrazones on diazotisation rearranged to anilides with a mechanism similar to Beckmann rearrangement of ketoximes. Hydrazone rearrangement is a stereospecific reaction and the group situated *anti* to NH₂ group migrates during rearrangement^{1,2}. Previous workers reported the rearrangement of hydrazones derived from *para*-substituted-benzophenones and -acetophenones³. However, rearrangement of hydrazones of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted-benzophenones and α -substituted-acetophenones is not reported in literature, except a very few attempts reported by the present author and coworkers⁴. Therefore, with a view to study the scope and utility of this reaction we undertook the work on diazotisation rearrangement of tosylhydrazones of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted-benzophenones, α -phenylacetophenones and disubstituted-benzophenones having one substituent in each ring.

Results and Discussion

In our present work, to avoid azine formation, the reaction was modified by converting the ketones (1a-i) directly into the tosylhydrazone (2a-i) by reacting with alcoholic solution of *p*-toluenesulphonylhydrazide. The tosylhydrazones (2a-i) on treatment with sulphuric acid (90%) and sodium nitrite underwent rearrangement to the anilides (3a-i). Scheme 1 is adopted for the rearrangement reaction. Hydrazones being unstable, it was not possible to get them in sufficient yield to carry out further reaction. Therefore, the ketones (1a-i) were converted into the tosylhydrazones (2a-i) which gave the anilides (3a-i). The structure of

the anilides (3a-i) was confirmed by elemental analyses and superimposable ir spectra with the authentic sample. The m.m.p. with the authentic sample was not lowered. All authentic samples were prepared by Schotten-Baumann condensation of the appropriate acid chloride with the corresponding amine in presence of NaOH (10%). In the ir spectra, the anilides generally absorbed at $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 360 (NH, str.), 1 660-640 (C=O, amide-I), 1 530 (NH, def. amide-II) and 1 320-1 340 cm⁻¹ (NH, amide-III).

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF TOSYLHYDRAZONES (2a-i) AND ANILIDES (3a-i)

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	M.p.* °C	Yield** %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
							C	H	N
2a	CH ₃	H	H	147 ^a	58	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	69.6 (69.23)	5.6 (5.49)	7.3 (7.69)
2b	Cl	H	H	161 ^a	52	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	62.8 (62.4)	4.2 (4.4)	7.28 (7.28)
2c	Br	H	H	126 ^a	57	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	56.2 (55.94)	4.3 (3.96)	6.7 (6.50)
2d	H	OCH ₃	H	157 ^a	50.2	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	66.9 (66.31)	5.3 (5.26)	6.8 (7.36)
2e	H	Cl	H	165 ^c	47	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	62.1 (62.4)	4.5 (4.42)	6.8 (7.28)
2f	H	Cl	Cl	170 ^a	54	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	56.9 (57.27)	3.8 (3.81)	6.1 (6.68)
2g	H	CH ₃	OH	130 ^a	42	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	70.1 (69.8)	6.1 (5.8)	6.9 (7.40)
2h	NO ₂	H	—	178 ^a	49	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	62.0 (61.6)	4.8 (4.6)	9.8 (10.26)
2i	H	Cl	—	160 ^b	52	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	62.9 (63.2)	5.1 (4.76)	7.2 (7.02)
3a	OH	H	H	124 ^e	71	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NO	79.7 (79.62)	6.6 (6.16)	6.4 (6.6)
3b	Cl	H	H	115 ^e	30	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ClNO	67.5 (67.38)	4.3 (4.31)	6.5 (6.04)
3c	Br	H	H	123 ^e	93 ^b	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ BrNO	56.1 (56.52)	3.6 (3.62)	5.4 (5.07)
3d	H	OCH ₃	H	120 ^e	84	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NO ₂	74.4 (74.00)	5.9 (5.72)	5.6 (6.16)
3e	H	Cl	H	134 ^f	63 ^d	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ClNO	67.8 (67.38)	4.5 (4.31)	5.9 (6.04)
3f	H	Cl	Cl	123 ^e	40	C ₁₃ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO	58.9 (58.6)	3.4 (3.38)	5.7 (5.26)
3g	H	OH	CH ₃	110 ^e	90 ^j	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO	80.3 (80.0)	6.2 (6.66)	6.0 (6.22)
3h	NO ₂	H	—	208 ^b	32	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄	65.4 (65.6)	4.8 (4.68)	11.4 (10.9)
3i	H	Cl	—	160 ^d	39 ^j	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClNO	68.4 (68.45)	5.0 (4.88)	6.2 (5.7)

*Solvent for crystallisation: ^aMeOH, ^bEtOH, ^cC₆H₆, ^dC₆H₆ + (C₂H₅)₂O, ^eaq. EtOH, ^fC₆H₆ + petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), ^gC₆H₆ + CHCl₃. **Eluent, ^hC₆H₆–CHCl₃ (1:1), ⁱC₆H₆–petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)(1:1), ^jC₆H₆–Et₂O (2:1).

Experimental

The starting ketones except **1i** were prepared by the methods described in literature⁵.

The preparation of the reagent, *p*-toluenesulphonylhydrazide was done by the reported method⁶ with the modification that the addition of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride was done at 0° to avoid the formation of higher melting hydrazine-di (*p*-toluenesulphonate).

The general procedures for the preparation of the tosylhydrazones (2a–i) and their diazotisation rearrangement to the anilides (3a–i) are given below.

Tosylhydrazone of 3,4'-dimethylbenzophenone (2g) : 3,4'-Dimethylbenzophenone (2 g), *p*-toluenesulphonyl hydrazide (2.4 g) and methanol (25 ml) were refluxed for 1 h and the reaction mixture was then concentrated and kept overnight. The resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from methanol in prisms (2g ; 1.5 g), m.p. 130°.

3,4'-Dimethylbenzanilide by rearrangement of tosylhydrazone of 3,4'-dimethylbenzophenone (3g) : To sulphuric acid (90% ; 18 ml) cooled to 0° by

freezing mixture with constant stirring by a magnetic stirrer, was added solid sodium nitrite (1.5 g) in small portions with stirring at 0–2°. 3,4'-Dimethylbenzophenonetosylhydrazone (0.8 g) was then added to the mixture in small portions over a period of 45 min and temperature raised to 10°. When the addition was completed the mixture was stirred for further 30 min raising the temperature to 40°. It was then neutralised with ice-cold liquor ammonia (33 ml) and the separated brownish solid was filtered, washed with water and purified by column chromatography over silica gel. On eluting with benzene–ether (2:1), a gummy solid was obtained which was crystallised from aqueous ethanol to give colourless crystals (3g ; 0.4 g), m.p. 110°. M.m.p. with the authentic sample was not lowered. The authentic sample was prepared by Schotten–Baumann condensation of *p*-toluidine with 3-methylbenzoyl chloride in presence of NaOH (10%).

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References

1. D. E. PEARSON and C. M. GREER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1895.
2. D. L. FISHEL and B. L. HAWBECKER, "Abstracts of Papers" Division of Organic Chemistry, American Chemical Society, 156th. National Meeting, Atlantic City, September 1968, Paper no. 170.
3. D. E. PEARSON, K. N. CARTER and C. M. GREER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **75**, 5905; B. L. HAWBECKER, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1970, **47**, 218; V. JOSHI and M. I. HARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 999.
4. V. JOSHI, S. S. JALISATGI and M. I. HARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 83.
5. E. B. WOMACK, N. CAMPBELL and G. B. DODDS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1404; SMITH, *Chem. Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 4047, K. V. AUWERS, M. LECHNER and H. BUNDESMANN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1925, **58**, 50, W. R. CATECART, V. MEYER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 3293, F. ULLMANN and I. GOLDBERG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 2813, H. A. STAAB and E. JOST, *Justus Liebig's Ann. Chem.*, 1962, **655**, 90, H. L. HALLER, P. D. BARTLETT, N. L. DRAKE, M. S. NEWMAN, S. J. CRISTOL, C. M. EAKER, R. A. HAYES, G. W. KILMER, B. MAGERLEIN, G. P. MUELLER, A. SCHNEIDER and W. WHEATLEY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1591; W. SCHARWIN and SHORIGIN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 2025.
6. A. ALBERT and R. ROYER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1150.